

EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES OF CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS AND FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ART FIELD OF YOUTH

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Abstract. *This article reveals the specific aspects of the formation of human personality and the organization of educational processes in the context of cultural events. Also, the specificity of attracting young people to creativity, providing artistic knowledge on art types has been thoroughly analyzed on the example of music clubs.*

Keywords: *cultural and educational institutions, spirituality, spiritual education, music, amateur circle, the principle of vitality and authenticity, the principle of nationalism, the principle of mass and voluntariness, the principle of scientificity and creativity.*

Today, Uzbekistan, which is recognized as a social state, has many cultural and educational institutions, including cultural centers, cultural palaces, museums, libraries, culture and recreation parks, which have unique opportunities in the spiritual education of young people. It is impossible to educate people in places without using the opportunities of cultural and educational institutions, because these institutions are a unique center of spiritual and creative activity among the people.

Problems in the spiritual education of young people are spiritual poverty, narrow-mindedness, bigotry, dishonesty, injustice, lack of faith, impurity, lack of compassion, and the rejection of such vices as a way for people to decide on a policy based on high culture and national spiritual values. Eliminating it should become the main task of cultural and educational institutions.

National independence has created a very large and important social-political, cultural-ideological basis for building a democratic society in our country. At the same time, the conclusion that it is impossible to strengthen independence without cultural and educational activities carried out by the government and members of the society made independence a reality, a certain social event guaranteed to be fulfilled. It is becoming clear to everyone that all socio-economic, political, moral and ideological reforms taking place in society can reach their perfection only through cultural means.

The fact that spiritual factors have become a priority today is also due to the democratic processes taking place in society. In fact, culture is a social force that further enlivens democracy, gives it creative power, and ultimately creates deep positive changes in the life of society, their harmony is the basis of a fair and just state.

During the years of independence, the government of Uzbekistan also paid attention to socio-political, economic, territorial democratic conditions in the cultural policy of the country. Taking into account that the majority of the population lives in rural areas, cultural and educational activities were a clear manifestation of a fair cultural policy in Uzbekistan. Therefore, increasing the number of rural culture houses, palaces, and club institutions, improving their work efficiency can be considered as priority areas of activity in this field.

At the same time, they are highly effective and serve to fulfill the urgent tasks of satisfying the spiritual needs of the rural population, restoring our national values, meaningfully spending the free time of the population, educating the young generation in the spirit of high patriotism, and conveying to them the essence of independence. The accumulated experience and their results showed that a new management model has emerged that is effective in the management of cultural and spiritual affairs in rural areas.

During the years of independence, the republic's cultural and educational institutions conducted their activities based on the requirements of independence. These institutions operate on the basis of the following principles:

1. Vitality and authenticity;
2. Populism and nationality;
3. Public and voluntary;
4. Science and creativity.

At the same time, special attention was paid to education of such qualities as patriotism and nationalism, enlightenment, bigotry and progressivism, honesty and intelligence, faith and wisdom, internationalism and ethics.

Literature, visual arts, sculpture, music and other types of art rich in national traditions should be paid attention to. Art has a great educational value in educating young people, and cultural institutions still need to do a lot in this regard. For this purpose, it will be necessary to review the activity, structural structure and regulations of the circles related to various fields of art opened under cultural institutions.

Another task facing cultural institutions is to create systems of internal aesthetic education. These systems determine the overall development of a person. This is a defined system of knowledge, that is, the content of aesthetic education, first of all, a unit of three tasks according to the collective, systematic implementation - scientific, developmental, psychological and pedagogical processes, taking into account the demands of society in the educational process, in a new way it is necessary to apply knowledge and find content based on rules. Based on them, a direction is determined in relation to the personality of each young person. To achieve these goals, it is possible to study some types of art, world and national culture, and other forms of education in a circle with young people. In the programs of art circles in cultural institutions, attention should be paid to the formation of personal education, teaching to live with moral responsibility. It is necessary to teach young people of middle and senior age to improve their knowledge and skills independently. It is necessary to find new forms and content of aesthetic education. In particular, it is desirable to study the theory and history of folklore, national ensembles, national dances and songs, national-traditional types of art, restore the ancient methods and methods of aesthetic education.

Special treatment should be given to gifted and talented pupils. Wide use of public events, conversations, meetings with representatives of culture and art, conference, reports, "Navroz", "Song Festival", "Dance Festival", "Meeting with children's composers", "Song A trip to the world", "History of one song", "Night of Yalla and laparlar", "Festival of folk songs", "Maqom night", "Meeting with stage masters", "Meeting of three generations" gave results [1.-B.188.].

The lifestyle of Uzbek people has changed to an unprecedented extent in recent years. Now, today's man is on his own path of living a good life, showing beautiful examples of

communication, and most importantly, aesthetic mastering of reality. At the same time, it has a significant impact on the development of musical culture.

There are usually two approaches to the educational nature of music. First, music is a moving and purifying spiritual phenomenon. Second, music is a source of interest based on entertainment and pastime. In both approaches, the participation of music in educational processes is important. Because, if we take a rational approach to the issue, just as any music does not become a spiritual phenomenon, not all music is simply a source of interest. True music as a property of culture and spirituality is closer to educational processes. The educative nature of music is explained through the system of aesthetic culture, such as listening, feeling, reacting to it.

Today's music is a reflection of all the processes taking place in the world, it is the only way for a person and humanity to be freed from various external influences, sometimes from the spiritual, spiritual, social and physical sides, and is an opportunity for the gradual development of human culture. New music, like new art, did not appear at a certain time, it is a continuation of the previous ones. But in some cases, some pop music samples try to forcefully influence the moral world of young people. They are mainly samples or imitations of Western music. Some types of modern ultra music ("beat", "rock", "rap", "pop") are leading young people to spiritual poverty and downfall. Some "samples" of such absurd and obscene music have reached us. Although we accept the fact that Western music is rapidly entering the lives and minds of our youth as a novelty, it is true that a serious change is being made in their character. We cannot deny that Western music genres are suitable for the upbringing and lifestyle of young people. Their taste demands that. But young people who are hysterical, who repeat the same words a lot, and listen to music based on the same rhythm, will undoubtedly distance themselves from nationalism. Loud music settles in their consciousness to such an extent that, as a result, their behavior begins to change. Therefore, it is an important task of our society to educate young people to have the correct aesthetic taste, love for real beautiful music that enriches the spiritual world of a person, and to develop a new human being - the builder of an independent state. Because the influence of the art of music on the mind and spiritual world of people is extremely great.

Our cultural community, first of all, musicologists, artists, composers, writers and journalists, and a large number of art lovers, openly express their opinions on such issues, and in this way, we owe it to our youth to educate them properly. is also obligatory.

The question of what should be done to increase the educational influence and importance of national music is a cross-cutting question. Hasan Rajabi, the people's hafiz of Uzbekistan, answers him as follows: "If a child is taught our national values, language, and musical works from a very young age, he will be considered to have enriched his mind by the time he reaches school age. Kindergarten-age children should be played with national musical tunes every now and then in a way that they do not tire their ears when they are eating and playing. There are even ways to learn the old Uzbek literary language, that is, some of the words used by our classic poets. Children's intelligence, which quickly accepts things, gradually develops. We don't understand why Alisher Navoi, because we start referring to the poet's work at the age of 11-12. If we inculcate our classical music in a child from the age of 2-3, 4-5, he would not accept status and lyrical songs with a stiff neck when he gets older. In this way, his mind and thinking develop until he graduates from school. School-age children should be introduced to music listening hours. A child who has developed a culture of listening and feeling skills will never put aside his national music and love

the art of foreigners. I want this tradition to be transferred from school to colleges and lyceums, to higher educational institutions" [2.-B.17.].

It is impossible to recover lost opportunities in the education of morals and manners. Only well-educated children are willing to learn and can find their proper place in society. Our society needs educated young people who conscientiously strive to master the fundamentals of science. Such qualities can be formed only on the ground of mature morals and manners. It is necessary to form qualities such as a sense of duty, responsibility towards the homeland and the nation, as well as compliance with laws. Eliminating the environment that negatively affects the development of young people as a person is part of the system of educational work. Educating young people is a public work in which the whole community is interested. Implementation of education and training by the state is also an objective necessity required by the needs of the future. [3.-B.151.] To give proper musical education to our children from childhood and to form noble ideas in the hearts and minds of the young generation, to educate them in the spirit of love for the motherland, respect for our national values, and self-sacrifice. A large number of music schools, ethnographic communities, and choral circles were established. One of them is "Bulbulcha" children's musical troupe, which is popular not only in Uzbekistan, but also in neighboring countries and far abroad. In recent years, many pageants, cultural and educational events, concerts, exhibitions and festivals aimed at discovering, supporting and encouraging young talents have been held in the Republic. For example, such contests as "Art Buds", "You are the only one, the Holy Motherland", "Yangi Avlod", "Nihal" can be cited.

Electronic musical instruments, which are the fruit of the era of technological development and globalization, are getting absorbed into our national musical culture. Afghan rubob, synthesizers, pianos and accordions, microphones have become an integral part of our musical culture. Integration processes in such musical instruments are especially common in the pop genre. A number of groups appeared in the Uzbek variety scene, for example, Muhridin Holikov, Nuriddin Haydarov, Mahmud Namozov enriched the Uzbek folk music culture with modern principles after "Yalla". As a result, especially after independence, new, modern aesthetic values were formed in our musical culture.

Therefore, in modern times, in music schools, amateur clubs, cultural and educational institutions, it is required to take into account world standards in the correct solution of educational and professional skills issues.

The rapid pace of changes in society creates a huge flow of information, which requires the use of new technologies in the educational system. Therefore, the computer is widely used in various fields of human activity, including music and art. The use of computers in the educational process leads to revision of existing ideas, rejection of outdated schemes, change of some methodological views.

The criteria for the structure of the musical program should mainly be in the following form:

- a) electronic equipment, a computer cannot replace the teacher, because the student learns the main part of the educational material under the direct guidance of the teacher;
- b) the use of a computer in the educational process makes it possible to connect concrete-practical (singing, working with a sheet of music) and abstract-theoretical activities;

c) computer programs do not have to reproduce all educational material. Perhaps the logical-spiritual aspects of the studied topic should be studied at the level of computer capabilities [4.-B.81.].

As a conclusion, it should be noted that technical devices can never replace playing a certain instrument by heart in cultural education. In turn, artistic education increases the logical thinking ability of young people and is inextricably linked with expressive means of influence (image, color, sound, graphics, movement, composition). In the activities of musical clubs in cultural institutions, the content of formation of concepts of the national idea among young people was studied.

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